

A AYURVED CONCEPT OF GARBINI PARICHARYA***¹Dr. Akanksha Chandel, ²Dr. Vivek Mahalwar**¹Associate Professor, ²Associate Professor ¹Department of Prasuti Tantra & Striroga, ²Department of Prasuti Tantra & Stririga, ^{1,2}Government Medical Ayurved College Bilaspur (C.G).**How to cite this Article:** *Dr. Akanksha Chandel, Dr. Vivek Mahalwar. (2025). A Ayurved Concept of Garbini Paricharya. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 11(11), 8–12.
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ABSTRACT

Infertility varies across the regions of the world, and it has been estimated to affect 8 to 12% couples worldwide. It tends to be the highest in countries with high fertility rates. The WHO has estimated the overall prevalence of primary infertility in India to be between 3.9 and 16.8%. Endometriosis, a cause of female infertility, is a condition in which endometrial tissue, the tissue that lines the inside of the uterus, grows outside the uterus and attaches to other organs in the abdominal cavity, such as the ovaries and fallopian tubes. Endometriosis is a progressive disease that tends to get worse over time and can recur after treatment. Symptoms include painful menstrual periods, abnormal menstrual bleeding, and pain during or after sexual intercourse. Endometriosis causes infertility in different ways. If the endometriosis damages the tubes and the ovaries, then this will significantly reduce the woman's ability to conceive. This will significantly alter the movement of the egg and sperm. There is no single cause of infertility in endometriosis, but rather several factors that decrease the chances for conception. In advanced endometriosis (Stage III-IV), endometriomas (chocolate cysts) or pelvic adhesions interfere mechanically with ovulation and ovum/embryo transport. In early endometriosis (Stage I-II), the mechanism of infertility is less clear and more complex. Vandhyatva has been described by the Acharyas in an extensive sense, including nidana and chikitsa. In the curative aspect, numerous treatments have been mentioned. Still, it is unclear which type of infertility or specific factor, such as Ritu, Kshetra, Ambu, or Beeja, they will act upon. Nowadays, it is essential to evaluate everything separately. The anatomical descriptions in Ayurvedic literature differ from those in modern medical science. The manner in which bodily organs are defined is based more upon the principles than the structures.

KEYWORDS: Endometriosis, Ovary, Fallopian tubes, Endometrioma, Kshetra.**INTRODUCTION**

Garbhini individual where in garbha dwells or halts of garbha is termed as garbhini. Paricharya the word "paricharya" is determine as garbhini. paricharya the word "paricharya" is derived from the root "chara-gatau" with prefix "pari". charya, that means to service or nuthe garbhini paricharya is the care given to a pregnant woman in a necessary, all respectful manner it's very important for future social impact assessment Pregnancy is the most critical part of every woman's life. Garbhini paricharya explains in detail about the month-wise dietary regimen and prescriptions (maasaanumasik pathya), substances that are beneficial to pregnancy (garbasthapak dravyas) and activities and substances that are harmful (garbhopghaatkar bhavas),

various foods and activities that are prescribed and proscribed, according to their effects on the fetus are also explained. So systematic Examination, Dietary and other advice are very important; this systematic supervision is called as Garbhini Paricharya (Anti Natal Care). Supervision should be regular and periodic in nature and according to need of Garbhini (ANC Mother). Ayurveda considers food to be the best source of nourishments as well as medication for the pregnant woman. The nine monthly diet is unique concept in Ayurveda. It changes in accordance with the growth of the foetus in the womb and at the same time ensures health of the mother. The things which are contraindicated in pregnancy are known as Garbhopaghatakara Bhavas and avoidance of these things is necessary for wellbeing of foetus. In this paper

we have described monthly dietary regimen and Living style for whole pregnancy according to Samhita.

Caraka says that the pregnant woman desirous of producing a thorough (healthy and good looking) child should give up non congenial diet and mode of life and protect herself by doing good conduct and using congenial diets and mode of life.

Masanumasika Pathya

(Month Wise Dietary Regimen): During pregnancy foetus starts to get nutrition from mother through placenta. Adequate nutrition is needed for monthly constant and proper growth of embryo. The requirement of nutrition varies according to developmental stage of foetus month wisely (Masanumasika vrudhi). Pregnancy imposes the extra nutrients requirement. Thus the dietetic

requirements of the mother also changes month wise. By following these dietetic regimens prescribed, the pregnant woman remains healthy and delivers a baby having good health, energy, strength, complexion and voice. The baby would also be well-built. Having importance of this; in Ayurvedic samhitas, the month wise dietetic regimen is given in details known as masanumasika paricharya (monthly regimen) for woman right from the first month up to the ninth month of pregnancy. The monthly regimen is necessary to make pelvis, waist, sides of the chest, back, healthy & flexible and downward movement of vata (vata anulomana) - this is needed for the normal delivery, Normalization of the urine and stool and their elimination with ease, Promotion of strength and complexion, Delivery with ease of a healthy baby, endowed with excellent qualities in proper time (280 days).

Month s

	CHARAKA	SUSHRUTA	ASHTANGA SANGARHA	HARIT
1st Month	Non medicated milk 5	Madhur, Sheet, Liquid Diet 6	Medicated milk7	Madhuyashti, madhukapuspa with butter, honey and sweetened milk8
2nd Month	Milk medicated with madhura rasa (sweet taste)	drugs Same as first month	Same as Charaka Milk medicated with madhura rasa (sweet taste)	Sweetened milk treated with kakoli12
3rd Month	Milk with honey and ghrita	Same as first month	Milk with honey and ghrita	Krisara
4th Month	Milk with butter extracted from milk in the quantity of one <i>aksha</i> or milk with butter.	cooked sasti rice with curd, dainty and pleasant food mixed with milk & butter and Jangal mansa	Cooked Milk with one tola (12gm) of butter	Medicated cooked rice
5 month	Month Ghrita prepared with butter extracted from milk	Cooked shastika rice with milk, jangal mansa along with dainty food mixed with milk and ghrita	Same as Charaka	Payasa
6th Month	Ghrita prepared from milk medicated with madhura (sweet) drugs	Ghrita or rice gruel medicated with gokshura	Same as Charaka	Sweetened curd
7th Month	Same as in sixth month	Ghrita medicated with prithakaparnyadi group of drugs	Same as charaka	Ghritakhanda (a sweet dish)
8th Month	KshiraYawagu mixed with ghrita	Asthanabasti with decoction of badari mixed with bala, atibala, satapuspa, patala etc., honey and ghrita. Asthan is followed by Anuvasana basti with oil medicated with milk, madhura drugs	Kshirayawagu mixed with ghrita, asthanabasti with decoction of badari, anuvasana basti with oil medicated with Madura drugs	Ghritapuraka
9th Month	Anuvasanabasti with oil prepared with drugs of Madhura (sweet) group, vaginal tampon of this oil	Unctuous gruels and jangal mansa rus up to the period of delivery38 Same as Charaka39 Different varieties of cereals	rice gruel prepared with milk and mixed with <i>ghruta</i> should be given.	different varieties of cereals should be used.

Garbhiupadhaka bhava

Garbhini should avoid use of teekshna, rooksha, ushna dravyas. Should give up foul smelling articles and should not eat dried up, stale, putrefied or wet food, Vistambhi (hard to digest), vidahi food as these are harmful for the foetus. She should avoid heavy exercises, coitus, harsh or violent activities, ride over vehicles, excess satiation,

excess emaciation, sleeping in day and awakening in night, sitting in uneven places and should avoid fasting, grief, anger, visiting lonely places, cremation ground, prolonged stay near fire or hot sun etc.

Her sleeping and sitting place should be covered with soft cushion/mattress. All these psychological and

physical strains like carrying heavy weight or vehicle riding may precipitate abortion due to sudden increase in intra-abdominal pressure. Susruta in 8th month of pregnancy has indicated asthapana basti with decoction of badari mixed with bala, atibala, sathapushpa, pestle sesamum seeds, milk, curd, mastu, oil, salt, madhanaphala, honey and ghrita, followed by anuvasana. basti of oil medicated with milk and decoction of madhura group of drugs for clearing the retained faeces and anulomana of vayu. Due to the movement of vayu in right direction the lady delivers without difficulty and remains free from complications. Whereas charaka and vagbata, in 9th month has advised anuvasana basti with oil medicated with madhura group of drugs and vaginal tampons with the same oil used for sthana and garbhamarga (vaginal canal and perineum). Charaka⁴⁹ and vagbata⁵⁰ have advised aindri, brahmi, satavirya, sahasravirya or durva, amogha, avyatha, siva, arista, vatyapuspi, viswaksena for oral use with milk or ghritha prepared with these drugs. These drugs can also be kept in close contact of body or used in the form amulets to be tied in head or right arm. Anuvasanavasti for lubrication of garbha.

3. Garbhasthapaka dravyas

Garbhasthapaka dravyas counter act the effect of the garbhopaghatakar bhavas and help in the proper maintenance of the garbha. Garbhini should avoid use of teekshna, rooksha, ushna dravyas. Should give up foul smelling articles and should not eat dried up, stale, putrefied or wet food, vistambhi (hard to digest), vidahi food as these are harmful for the foetus. She should avoid heavy exercises, coitus, harsh or violent activities, ride over vehicles excess satiation, excess emaciation, sleeping in day and awakening in night, sitting in uneven places and should avoid fasting, grief, anger, visiting lonely places, cremation ground prolonged stay near fire or hot sun etc. Her sleeping and sitting place should be covered with soft cushion/mattress. All these psychological and physical strains like carrying heavy weight or vehicle riding may precipitate abortion due to sudden increase in intra-abdominal pressure. Susruta in 8th month of pregnancy has indicated asthapana basti with decoction of badari mixed with bala, atibala, sathapushpa, pestle sesamum seeds, milk, curd, mastu, oil, salt, madhanaphala, honey and ghrita, followed by anuvasana basti of oil medicated with milk and decoction of madhura group of drugs for clearing the retained faeces and anulomana of vayu. Due to the movement of vayu in right direction the lady delivers without difficulty and remains free from complications. Whereas charaka and vagbata, in 9th month has advised anuvasana basti with oil medicated with madhura group of drugs and vaginal tampons with the same oil used for sthana and garbhamarga (vaginal canal and perineum). Charaka and vagbata have advised aindri, brahmi, satavirya, sahasravirya or durva, amogha, avyatha, siva, arista, vatyapuspi, viswaksena for oral use with milk or ghritha prepared with these drugs. These drugs can also be kept in close contact of body or used in the form

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Dietetics and mode of life contraindicated for pregnant women or garbhopghatakar bhavas i.e. factors likely to harm the fetus

charaka says pregnant lady should avoid the pungent things excessive exercise and coitus following factors are harmful for the fetus such as –use of excessive hot, heavy and pungent substances; harsh or violent activities, (activities much beyond one's own capacity) and others as instructed by elder persons, she should not wear red colored garments for protection from God, demons, and their followers as evil spirit should not use intoxicating substances and wine, ride over vehicle (running on uneven paths), use of meat (excessive) and give up the things contrarily to indriyas and other harmful articles, the things should also be given up as instructed by old ladies sushruta had said that from the day of the conception the woman should totally give up the coitus, exercise, excessive satiation (santarpan or anabolic), emaciation (apatarpana or catabolic), sleeping in day and awakening in night, grief, riding on vehicle, fear, squatting or the posture of sitting on the hams with the soles of feet touching the ground (utkattaasana), and avoid untimely use of snehana (oleation), bloodletting and suppression of natural urges. The coitus troubles the fetus. she should not touch the dirty or disfigured persons possessing less body parts, should give up foul smelling, awful looking substances and exciting stories, should not eat dried up, stale, putrefied or wet (moistened) food. She should avoid outing, visit of lonely places, chaitya haunted tree, cremation ground or shade of a tree, acts likely to promote anger and disgrace, talking in high pitch, etc. all the things likely to harm the fetus. Repeated excessive massage of oil and unguents should not fatigue herself. vagbhata had corroborated the views of charaka, however alike sushruta he had also given the list of contraindications as- coitus, exercise, emaciation, trauma, conveyances. Carriage or animals causing excessive jerks, night awakening, day sleeping, suppression of natural urges, indigestion, prolonged stay in hot sun and near fire, anger, grief, fear, terror, fasting, squatting, or other abnormal hard postures, falling in pits and wells, looking or hearing disliked things etc. The parents especially woman desirous of having offspring of high quality and virtues should make themselves superior. In first month, massage of oil and unguents and up to fifth month use of articles likely to aggravate doshas should be avoided.

Yogaratanakar, in kshirdosha chikitsa had contraindicated use of sudation, emesis, kshara, along with polluted and incompatible food. Cleansing measures are contraindicated in pregnant woman.

All these contraindications can be grouped under following headings.

1. those which produce psychological or physical strain

such as grief, exercise, etc. though normal coitus and exercise are beneficial, however, their excessive use or psychological trauma may precipitate abortion specially in ladies prone for the same.

2. Avoidance of visit to cremation ground etc. sudden shock may produce abnormality specially abortion.

3. Over weight carrying or vehicle riding may precipitate abortion due to sudden increase in intra-abdominal pressure; prolonged squatting in abnormal postures and supine position may influence placental and uterine blood flow (due to pressure of gravid uterus on iliac vessels) thus cause abortion, intrauterine death of the other abnormalities.

4. Deitetic regulations- *rasaj bhaava* – diet of pregnant mother is very important for maintenance of her own health, proper nourishment and growth of the fetus. Texts have contraindicated use of meat, while it is already advised by *sushruta* in fourth and fifth month, thus here excessive use of meat of aquatic animals should be taken. Wine in use harms the fetus. It is difficult to explain contraindication for use may produce digestive abnormalities.

5. Use of over satiation may excessively increase the body weight of mother and fetus, overeating is one of the causes of pregnancy toxemia. Over weight of fetus may cause difficulty in labour.

DISCUSSION

Vagbhata use of *prajasthapan* drugs described in *sutrasthana* after *pumsavahan karma*, *indu* says that these drugs prevent abortion *lii charaka* and *kashyap* have prescribed certain drugs during pregnancy without specifying their indications, period or method of use. *Chakrapaniliii* had clarified that *Garbhasthaapak* drugs- are those which after counteracting the effects of harmful factors (*garbhopghaatkar bhaavas*) for fetus helps in its proper maintenances, thus these can be considered as a treatment for abortion. *Kashyap* had said these to be used in routine by pregnant woman, routine use of these drugs might be beneficial for maintenance of proper health, growth and development of mother and fetus respectively, with this idea the drugs are being enumerated here. *Charaka* and *vagbhata* have given the specific use of this enlisted drug as oral use of milk and *ghrutam* prepared with these drugs. The bath with the cold decoction of these drugs during *pushya nakshatra amlute* and *trivirta* should also be tied to the pregnant women waist should also be taken, these drugs should also be kept in close contact of mother and amulets of this be tied in head or right arm (only *charaka*). Similarly the drugs of *Jivaniya* group should also be used. *Kashyapa* had advocated listed drugs should be uprooted with enchantation of mantras and tied as amulet during *pushya nakshatra*, waist of pregnant woman.

sushruta had described almost similar things under the heading of *dauhruda*. Actually there is no difference between these descriptions, because the pregnant woman will eat only when she has longings for these things, or has *dauhruda* since these are likely to produce certain

abnormalities in fetus, hence can be grouped under harmful category. The woman possessing two hearts (one of her own and other of the fetus) is called *dauhrudini*. the period of *dauhruda* and specific longings during this period is elaborately described in ayurved classics. *Bhel* had advised to examine *dauhruda* of fetus by congenial diet. Life begins with conception even nine months prior to the delivery. Entire gestational period is important for achievement of healthy baby along with prevention of complications during pregnancy. *Dauhrudavastha* is the special concept of Ayurveda affecting fetal growth. It is the period during which pregnant woman (*Dauhrudini*) expresses dietary and behavioural desires. These longings are desires of fetus, fulfillment of which is beneficial for proper gestation, whereas nonfulfillment or ignorance causes various developmental anomalies.

CONCLUSION

By the above details, it is clear that milk and drugs of *Madhura* group have been advised for entire pregnancy period. Milk is a wholesome diet. It provides nutrition and stability to the foetus. The drugs of *Madhura* group are having anabolic property. Hence, the use of these drugs will help in maintenance of proper health of *Garbhini* and development of foetus. So, the a *The Garbhini* who follows the such said *Upakramas* creates *Snigdha guna garbhini Avastha*, that *Snigdha guna* predominantly of *Kapha Dosh* and *Kppha Dosh* plays important role in nourishment which gains strength and delivers normally and easily without any complication.

All the discussions about the dietary and behavioral and medicinal regimen prescribed by all ayurved classics aims at the healthy progeny and avoiding pregnancy induced complications. These regimens help in the known cases of secondary infertility and cases of recurrent abortions. Do's and don'ts for pregnant lady shows the vigilant aspect of scholars and carefulness about the prevention of any adverse effect of food, drug, its interactions and incompatibility. *Dauhruda* should be completed and prescribed regimen if followed will results in the yield of desirous and happy entity.

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